

A Study of the Nature of Slope (S_v) of ϕ_v vs \sqrt{c} Curves for some Tetra-alkylammonium Salts in NMP-DMSO Solvent Mixture at 25°. Part-II

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By the use of magnetic float densitometer, the trend in the ϕ_v and hence the nature of the slope of ϕ_v vs \sqrt{c} curves has been studied for Et_4NI , Pr_4NI , Bu_4NI and Pen_4NI in NMP + DMSO mixtures in very dilute and in concentrated solutions at 25°. ϕ_v increases in dielectric constant of the medium or with increase in the salt concentration. All the four salts Et_4NI , Pr_4NI , Bu_4NI and Pen_4NI show transition in the sign of the slope in dilute as well as in concentrated range of solutions except for Bu_4NI which does not show such behaviour in concentrated solution.

Attempts¹ have been made to find out the possible causes for a negative slope, S_v , in the ϕ_v vs \sqrt{c} curves for the tetraalkyl ammonium and some common salts in high dielectric constant medium. It is recalled that these salts give positive slope in very low dielectric constant medium. To see the effect of dielectric constants on the S_v values, liquids of different dielectric constants were selected by earlier workers using different salts. It seemed interesting for us to examine this problem in the mixtures by selecting different suitable solvents and mixing them in different compositions to obtain the media of varying dielectric constants instead of selecting different liquids separately. Such studies were also carried out earlier in different water-solvent mixtures by different workers^{2,3}. It is to be pointed out that in all of these mixtures one solvent was taken as water and other one as non-aqueous. In our present study, the two different solvents are both non-aqueous ones, to investigate the problem of the slope with a different angle. Frank⁴ emphasised on the influence of water on S_v values by forwarding his hypothesis of enforcement of water structure around the electrolyte molecule due to hydrophobic R_4N^+ -ion-water interactions. So we thought of replacing water by some non-aqueous solvent and thus to compare the results of non-aqueous mixtures with those obtained in aqueous mixtures in order to see the similar effect of non-aqueous component of the solvent, if any, on the nature of the slope. In our previous publication⁵, one such non-aqueous solvent mixture, namely NMA + DMSO was taken to study tetraalkyl ammonium salts. A similar mixture NMP + DMSO (both constituents being non-aqueous) has been selected here to extend our studies further.

From the observations, ϕ_v vs \sqrt{c} curves are plotted for the low and high concentration ranges of the electrolyte. Only one such representative graph (Fig. 1) is given here. From these curves S_v (which is the slope of the curve) has been calculated for each curve. S_v values and the corresponding ϵ values for different solvent mixtures for all the salts are given in Table 2. The dielectric constants of NMP in DMSO at different compositions are not available in the literature. So, assuming a linear relationship to exist between dielectric constants and the composition, the dielectric constants of the mixture were computed. The composition and the corresponding ϵ values for different solvent mixtures are presented in Table 3. The plots of S_v vs ϵ are shown in Figs. 2 and 3.

TABLE 1—APPARENT MOLAL VOLUME OF TETRAETHYL AMMONIUM IODIDE

0% NMP in DMSO ($d_0 = 1.101232 \text{ g ml}^{-1}$)

Sl. no.	m	w g	i mA	d g ml ⁻¹	\sqrt{c}	ϕ_v cm ³ mol ⁻¹
Low concentration :						
1.	0.002	8.950	176	1.101399	0.047	164.25
2.	0.004	9.000	156	1.101566	0.066	164.65
3.	0.006	9.050	135	1.104730	0.081	164.80
4.	0.008	9.100	115	1.101895	0.094	165.05
5.	0.010	9.150	95	1.102060	0.105	165.10
6.	0.012	9.200	75	1.102220	0.115	165.40
High concentration :						
1.	0.02	9.300	45	1.102788	0.148	169.10
2.	0.04	9.350	87	1.104297	0.209	169.85
3.	0.06	9.600	17	1.105788	0.255	170.50
4.	0.08	9.700	20	1.107230	0.294	170.25
5.	0.10	9.800	37	1.108640	0.328	171.30
6.	0.12	9.900	49	1.110090	0.358	171.55

Results and Discussion

Apparent molal volume data are given in Table 1.

The salts Pr_4NI , Bu_4NI and Pen_4NI were studied in 0, 20, 40 and 60% NMP whereas we had

TABLE 2— S_V VALUES FOR SOME R_4NI -SALTS IN NMP+DMSO MIXTURES AT 25°

NMP (% v/v) in DMSO	Dielectric constant as manipulated by graph ϵ	S_V value ($\text{cm}^3 \text{mol}^{-3/2} \text{dm}^{1/2}$)							
		Et_4NI		Pr_4NI		Bu_4NI		Pen_4NI	
		Low	High	Low	High	Low	High	Low	High
0	46.6	17.10	11.90	5.88	1.82	6.25	1.45	13.51	3.45
5	52.6	8.00	3.37	—	—	—	—	—	—
10	59.0	6.82	2.91	—	—	—	—	—	—
20	71.6	5.10	1.43	-2.22	1.67	-1.40	0.91	-3.21	-2.40
40	97.6	—	—	-5.21	1.00	-6.35	0.56	-9.10	-5.64
60	123.0	—	—	-8.14	0.45	-11.20	0.31	-14.80	-8.60

TABLE 3—DIELECTRIC CONSTANTS OF NMP+DMSO MIXTURES AT 25°

Sl. no.	NMP (% v/v) in DMSO	Dielect. ϵ
1.	0	46.6
2.	5	52.6
3.	10	59.0
4.	20	71.6
5.	40	97.6
6.	60	123.0
7.	100	175.6

to select lower compositions of 0, 5, 10 and 20% NMP for Et_4NI due to solubility restrictions.

From the ϕ_V vs \sqrt{c} curves, it is clear that for a fixed salt and composition, ϕ_V is raised by increasing the concentration. ϕ_V also increases by increasing the NMP content in DMSO, i.e. increasing dielectric constant. The slope S_V of ϕ_V vs \sqrt{c} curves is positive, in all the four compositions, in case of Et_4NI . Pr_4NI and Bu_4NI when examined in low concentration range give positive slope in 0% NMP ($\epsilon=46.6$) and negative slope in other three mixtures 20% NMP ($\epsilon=71.6$), 40% NMP ($\epsilon=97.6$) and 60% NMP ($\epsilon=123$). In the high concentration range the same electrolytes give positive values of S_V in all the four mixtures.

 Fig. 1. ϕ_V vs \sqrt{c} curves for Et_4NI in NMP+DMSO mixtures at 25°; concentration range, 0.002–0.012 M.

For still large tetraalkyl ammonium salts, e.g. Pen_4NI , positive S_V value is obtained for pure DMSO (0% NMP) while the increase in the content of NMP results in a negative value of slope in both lower and higher concentrations. The results are more clear from the S_V vs ϵ curves (Figs. 2 and 3). Fig. 2 shows that except in case of Pr_4NI , the curves become more and more steeper from Et_4NI to Pen_4NI in dilute solutions. Fig. 3 indicates a reverse trend, i.e. except in the case of Pen_4NI the steepness diminishes as we go on from Et_4NI to Pen_4NI in concentrated solutions.

 Fig. 2. S_V vs ϵ curves for Et_4NI , Pr_4NI , Bu_4NI and Pen_4NI in NMP+DMSO mixtures at 25°; concentration range, 0.002–0.012 M.

Considering the slopes of these salts one by one individually, the behaviour of Et_4NI salt, in these varying dielectric constants-media became very uncertain owing to solubility restrictions. Though from Figs. 2 and 3, it seems that if this salt was soluble in all the selected compositions, it might have

shown a transition point at $\epsilon=104$ in dilute solutions and $\epsilon=82.8$ in concentrated solutions. But keeping the above restrictions in mind the results for Et_4NI should not be taken for granted.

Fig. 3. S_v vs ϵ curves for Et_4NI , Pr_4NI , Bu_4NI and Pen_4NI in NMP+DMSO mixtures at 25° ; concentration range, 0.02 - 0.12 M.

In case of Pr_4NI and Bu_4NI salts, the slope changes from positive to negative in low concentration region and transition points come out to be at $\epsilon=52.8$ and 63.2 respectively. Both these salts however do not show such a change in slope in concentrated solutions on the entire dielectric constant range studied. The behaviour of Pen_4NI is entirely different as the slope changes from positive to negative in both dilute and concentrated solutions. The behaviour of this salt is quite identical in both the cases; transition points being $\epsilon=56.8$ and 51.6 in low and high concentration ranges respectively.

If the results for Pr_4NI and Bu_4NI are examined more critically then there seems to be a peculiarity in the behaviour of these salts in the two regions of concentration. In high concentration region, both the salts have positive S_v values, but in dilute solutions these salts first give a positive slope and as the NMP content in DMSO is increased the slope becomes negative.

The increase of ϕ_v with the increase in salt concentration and the dependence of sign of slope on dielectric constant of the medium and the nature of the electrolyte ion are explained as below. There are mainly three factors which influence the ionic interactions in solutions at a given temperature, namely, the concentration of the salt, the nature and size of electrolyte ion, and the dielectric constant of the medium.

Generally, the increase of ϕ_v with the increase of salt concentration (that is a positive slope) is due to increase in the volume of solution on adding the salt (additive property). But it is not always true particularly when the bigger molecules, like higher tetraalkyl salts, are taken. The ionic interaction is very much affected due to interpenetration of ions (of solvent or electrolyte). The smaller ion penetrates into the void spaces formed by the cage of bigger ion and the addition of salt does not contribute towards the increase in volume. This results in the decrease of ϕ_v on increasing salt concentration (that is a negative slope). This explanation is valid upto a certain limit of concentration (the lower concentration range) but beyond this concentration limit (i.e. for higher concentration range), the additive property dominates over the interpenetration effect and again ϕ_v starts increasing with salt concentration. For very dilute solutions, the number of bigger ions is very small and the interpenetration of ions in such solutions is unable to start but no sooner the number of such ions increases a little more, the interpenetration effect sets in, causing a negative slope.

Furthermore, the ionic interactions depend very much on the dielectric constant of the medium (interaction forces are inversely proportional to the dielectric constant of the medium). In the medium of low dielectric constant the ionic interactions are strong but as the dielectric constant of the medium is increased interactions become weak. The high ionic interactions favour positive slope while the weak interactions lead to negative slope. Our results clearly indicate the dependence of dielectric constant on the S_v values giving the transition points in certain cases. So the behaviour of the electrolytes in this particular non-aqueous mixture is the resultant of all the three effects discussed here.

Experimental

N-Methyl propionamide (Fluka, purum) was fractionally crystallised and kept overnight over freshly ignited quicklime and then distilled under reduced pressure³; the middle fraction of the distillate was collected. The process of purification was repeated until the electrical conductance of the sample was reduced to about 10^{-6} mho or less. The solvent was stored in dark coloured bottles and used, as far as possible, the next day after distillation. The other solvent dimethyl sulphoxide (DMSO) was also purified in the manner as described earlier⁵. The tetraalkyl ammonium iodide salts were purified as detailed elsewhere⁶. Me_4NI is completely insoluble in this mixture, however, Et_4NI has a limited solubility in it. Its solutions are possible in pure DMSO and it is completely insoluble in pure NMP. By trial it was found out that solutions of required concentration range were possible upto 20% NMP in DMSO

and not beyond this composition. Solutions of Et₄NI in 0, 5, 10 and 20% NMP in DMSO (v/v) mixture were prepared.

Density of pure solvent mixtures was measured at 25° by the magnetic float densitometer technique⁷ by measuring the weights (w) on the magnetic float and corresponding hold-down current (i) for 0, 5, 10, 20, 40 and 60% NMP in DMSO mixtures, separately and then calculating density by the equation⁷,

$$d_{\text{solvent}}^{25} = \frac{W + w + f.i}{V^{25} + w/d_{\text{pt}}^{25}}$$

the terms have their usual meaning. These are d_0 values for the solvent mixtures.

The solutions of the electrolytes in these above solvent mixtures were then prepared on molal basis. As in the previous study⁸, two ranges of electrolyte concentrations, one being very dilute solutions (0.002—0.012M) and the other the concentrated ones (0.02—0.12M) were selected. The density (d) of these solutions were determined at 25° by the magnetic float densitometer in the same manner as described in the previous communication⁵ and as detailed above in the case of different solvent mixtures. Knowing the values of d and d_0 , the apparent molal volume (ϕ_v), was calculated for each solution by the usual formula,

$$\phi_v = \frac{1000(d_0 - d)}{m d d_0} + \frac{M}{d}$$

where m and M have their usual meaning. The

observations are recorded in Table 1 for pure DMSO, given as an example⁸.

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8. Other Tables may be obtained from the authors on request.